

Data Management Plan Information

ENHANCEMENT OF UV STABILITY OF THERMALLY MODIFIED WOOD THROUGH ENVELOPE IMPREGNATION WITH NANO BASED STABILISERS

Thermal modification is a process which improves the properties of wood, resulting in a material that can be disposed at the end of the product life cycle without presenting an environmental hazard. However, exposure to daylight causes brightening or graying of heat-treated wood surfaces. In order to tackle this challenge, we are proposing a novel way to improve the UV stability of thermally modified wood using nano based stabilizers. But instead of coating nanoparticles on heat treated wood, wood surfaces will be treated with nanoparticle (ZnO or CeO₂) solutions, thereby forming protective envelope on a wooden surface, which will be further heat treated under controlled temperature and time.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

H2020-MSCA-IF-WF-2018

Organisations

University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty

Researchers

Kavyashree Srinivasa

Datasets

Title: NewSiest_DMP

Template: Horizon 2020

External References

Data Repositories

External Datasets

Registries

Services

Dataset Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Purpose of data collection/generation: To study the optimal nanoparticle (NP) concentration and thermal modification conditions to improve the UV stability of wood surfaces. Data will be useful for academic and scientific readers and also has construction, industrial importance. Relation to objectives of project: The main research objectives of the action are: i) to introduce and optimize envelope treatment of wood with UV protecting nanoparticles ii) to set up the process of heat treatment of wood with nanoparticles in the envelope iii) to evaluate UV and fungal resistance of the novel wood-based material for industrial/commercial application. The collected data will therefore include: i) Experimental procedures and reaction conditions to achieve wood envelope treatment. Data on basic liquid properties of NP dispersion, retention and depth of penetration of the nanomaterial onto wood. ii) the generated data includes standard methodology of thermal modification of wood and data on percent mass loss, mechanical properties, contact angle variations, colour and chemical changes. iii) Data from evaluation of wood against light (UV) and fungal stability where change in wood properties will be accessed by weight loss, colour change, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), and changes in chemical constituents using FTIR spectroscopy.

1.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

Types and formats of data generated: 1. Envelope treatment of wood using nanosuspensions- ● Procedures: Word .doc(x), .txt ● Liquid properties of NP dispersion: Density, viscosity, surface tension, sedimentation using tensiometer, tables-.xls(x), .jpg/.jpeg/ .png or .pdf ● Particle size in dispersion: Dynamic light scattering (DLS), .xls(x) and .jpg/.jpeg/ .png or .pdf & UV-Vis spectroscopy, xls(x) and .jpg/.jpeg/ .png ● Treated samples: Uptake of liquid using tensiometer-.xls(x), water wettability using goniometer-.xls ● Retention data and penetration depth: excel sheet .xls (x), SEM images .tiff 2. Standardization of Thermal Modification- ● variation in temperature and time, mass loss, strength loss, colour and chemical change, dimensional stability, contact angle .xls and .jpg/.jpeg/ .png or .pdf 3.Evaluation of Light and Fungal stability- ● Light stability: Colour and chemical changes, contact angle

and surface hardness-.xls(x), .jpg/.jpeg/.png or .pdf • Fungal stability: Weight loss-.xls(x), .jpg/.jpeg/.png or .pdf, SEM-.tiff or .pdf.

1.3 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Data on thermal modification of spruce and beech in vacuum at host- to select the optimal reaction conditions for treatment. NO other existing data are expected to be re-used.

1.4 What is the origin of the data?

• Procedures: original lab notes which may be 10-50 kB. • Original measurements taken from the instruments available in the host organization and also necessary characterization methods to support the results from outside institutes/ universities.

1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

All the data, datasets and published articles generated from this action is estimated to consist of a maximum of 10-20GB of data.

1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

All the data generated from this action will be useful for research and industrial community.

2 FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

other

Comment: As per current knowledge of PI, there are no existing standards, vocabularies or methodologies for metadata. As metadata we will thus provide, -Project title -Author(s) -Abstract/ Description of content -Keywords -Version -Grant acknowledgement -Reference to publications

2.1.2 URL/Location

Zenodo, University of Ljubljana (UL) data repository

2.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Comment: No standard vocabularies will be utilised

2.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Comment: All data generated will be openly available once they are published in Zenodo/ UL data repository, which are linked with DOI.

2.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Comment: All data generated from this action along with suitable metadata information will be stored in an open access data repository eg. Zenodo and also University of Ljubljana (UL) data repository. A unique digital object identifier (DOI) will be given to each data uploaded to ease the identification mechanism.

2.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Comment: The following naming conventions will be used: Raw data-YYYYMMDD_[Experiment]_[Technique]_NNN; Processed results-YYYYMMDD_[Experiment]_[Technique]_NNN_[Analysis]. Symbols represent the following: YYYYMMDD: inverted date of the performed experiment day; Experiment: a short title of experimental series; Technique: title of technique used for characterization; NNN: a running number for individual samples

2.1.8 URL/Name

2.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

2.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

Comment: A unique digital object identifier (DOI) will be given to each data uploaded to ease the identification mechanism.

2.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

2.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes

Comment: All data will be accompanied with keywords. Repositories such as Zenodo allow for specifying a list of keywords to associate with the datasets.

2.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

OpenAIRE

2.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for some or all of your data?

No

2.1.18 Please describe the formats you plan to store your data in, including any URLs to documentation.

Commonly used format

Comment: .txt, .doc(x), .xls(x), .jpg/.jpeg/.png, .tiff, .pdf, .csv

2.1.19 Are the file formats you will use open?

all

2.1.22 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

fornodata

2.1.24 Please describe which data require proprietary tools to access the data?

2.1.25 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

Comment: data formats and contents are given by the equipment manufactures

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

2.2.2 Will all your data be openly accessible?

all

2.2.5 How will the data be made available?

Not Listed

Comment: Zenodo.org and data repository of the university

2.2.6 URL/Name

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.7 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

securewithbackupandrecovery

Comment: Original data will be stored locally for ease of use, but also on department and university servers and repositories with appropriate security and backup functionalities. No sensitive data is foreseen to be recorded during the action.

2.2.8 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

Comment: All raw and processed data will be published in proprietary file format (eg. PDF exports) and exported open format (eg. .csv, .txt or .md).

2.2.11 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

publication

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Will you use a standard vocabulary for your data types?

none

Comment: Data will also be published in .CSV format which is one of the most readable formats for information storage, supported by majority of software for numerical and data analysis.

2.3.3 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

Comment: Not relevant for the dataset generated from this action

2.4 Increase data reuse

2.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

after

2.4.4 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your data?

2.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

No

Comment: Data formats and contents are given by the equipment and software manufacturers. Loss of data is avoided through the secure storing procedures. Manipulation or loss of raw data is avoided through storing raw files after recording and only processing copies of the datasets, that are stored in a different location.

2.4.7 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

2.4.8 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

morethantenyyears

2.5 Allocation of resources

2.5.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

other

Comment: No expected cost for making data FAIR. Zenodo, an open access, service free repository will be used for making data FAIR.

2.5.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

Yes

Comment: Experienced researcher/ PI is responsible for data management.

2.5.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

institutionalarchive

Comment: All data resulting from this action which contributes to patent application or research publication are considered to be of long-term value and will be preserved. Data will be stored on Zenodo

and university repository as per the funder and institutional policies. A Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and associated metadata will be attached.

3 Data Security

3.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use
keptonsecure

Comment: Original data will be stored locally for ease of use, but also on department and university servers and repositories with appropriate security and backup functionalities.

4 Other

4.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?
No

Comment: Currently we are not using any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management.